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Research Article

**EXPERIENCE IN THE USE OF PHOTOACTIVATED
DISINFECTION OF CARIOUS CAVITIES BY TOLONIUM
CHLORIDE IN THE TREATMENT OF DEEP CARIOUS
LESIONS OF DENTIN**¹Razumova S.N., ²Aymaletdinova Z.T., ³Ivanova E.V., ⁴Saleeva G.T., ⁵Saleev R.D.¹ Professor, Peoples Friendship University of Russia, Moscow² Peoples Friendship University of Russia, Moscow³ Russian Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education, Therapeutic Dentistry Department,
Moscow⁴ Professor, Kazan State Medical University of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation,
Prosthetic Dentistry Department, Kazan⁵ Professor, Kazan State Medical University of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation,
Prosthetic Dentistry Department, Kazan**Abstract:**

The prevalence of caries among the adult population of the Earth, according to WHO, exceeds 90% and, as a rule, teeth of the chewing group are primarily affected because of their anatomical structure. A pilot study of the use of photoactivated disinfection of carious cavities with a solution of tolonium chloride showed high efficiency in the prevention of complications in the treatment of deep carious lesions of dentin.

Key words: *tooth decay, photoactivated disinfection, prevention, dentistry*

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INTRODUCTION:

The prevalence of caries among the adult population of the Earth, according to WHO, exceeds 90% and, as a rule, teeth of the chewing group are affected primarily because of their anatomical structure. Among the new methods of treatment of dental diseases, photodynamic therapy occupies a well-deserved place. Photodynamic therapy is based on the use of various photobiological effects caused by the

combined use of light, oxygen and a photosensitizer. In the clinic of therapeutic dentistry, the use of photodynamic therapy is due, first of all, to the need to influence various microorganisms that cause or contribute to the development of various inflammatory diseases. Also, the physiotherapeutic effect of laser radiation, realized by means of a mild localized rise in temperature, makes it possible to improve the efficiency of treatment.

Figure 1: The device of photodynamic therapy

The **aim** of the study was to determine the effectiveness of using the Lazurit diode laser device in the treatment of unspecified (deep) caries (K02.9).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study involved 40 patients aged 25-55 years who underwent treatment for deep caries without pulpitis symptoms (K02.9 caries, unspecified) in 1st Black class on molars of the lower jaw with EPT not exceeding 15 μ A. All patients before the start of treatment were assessed functional status (assessment of heart rate, blood pressure). Exclusion criteria were:

acute pulpitis (K04.0) of the teeth; decompensated states; refusal to participate in the study; oncological diseases.

Evaluation of the efficiency of photoactivated disinfection was determined according to the Citotest system: the immediate after the etching step, the cytological material was taken from the surface of the prepared carious cavity, and after irradiation with the Lazurit system. The results were counted in absolute scale.

Figure 2: Transport environment

Lazurit PAD® is a photoactivated disinfection that is used to improve the long-term results of restorations in the treatment of caries and in endodontic treatment by destroying all kinds of bacteria in the oral cavity, which allows to preserve demineralized tooth tissues and accelerate natural remineralization. This technology includes two elements: a medical solution of tonym chloride in low concentration and the device is a source of red light radiation of a certain wavelength for activation of the solution. Once introduced into the tooth tissues, molecules from the solution of tonym chloride attach to all the pathogens located there. After the solution is activated by light, the molecules of tonym chloride begin to release extremely active atomic oxygen, which "breaks through" the walls of pathogens, penetrating into the nucleus of the cell, destroying them.

After the formation of the cavity, etching was carried out and, according to a standard procedure, the prepared cavity was irradiated with a Lazurit apparatus at a power of 60 sec / 100 mW, the washing of the cavity after disinfection was performed with sterile water. Further restoration was carried out using an adhesive technique followed by restoration with a nanohybrid composite "Restavrin" (Technodent). Evaluation of the viability of the tooth was carried out with EPT after 1,2,3 and 6 months. The data were statistically processed using the Medstat program.

RESULTS OF THE STUDY:

It was shown that in normotonics (22 patients-55%) the parameters of EPT in unspecified caries were $10 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{A}$; in hypertensive patients (11 patients - 27.5%) - $14 \mu\text{A}$; in hypotonic patients (7 patients - 17.5%) - $9 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{A}$. Thus, on average, the EPT indices in case of unspecified caries before treatment were $11 \mu\text{A}$.

In the evaluation of the biomaterial before the use of photoactivated disinfection in 37 patients (92.5%), the cases were determined S. mutans and L. Casei. The data obtained by us on the viability of cultures after treatment with this method allows us to draw the following conclusions: Lazurit technology has a pronounced antimicrobial effect on S. mutans and L. Casei, since when the test was repeated after irradiation, the result was negative.

The dynamics of the change in EPT indices made up the reduction of indicators by 6 months in 38 patients (95%). Two patients with high blood pressure experienced a negative result in the form of classical pulpitis symptoms one day after treatment and an increase in EPT values to $45 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{A}$. Indirectly, this may indicate a restriction of the use of this method for deep dentin damage in patients with elevated blood pressure, but a small sample does not allow reliable results.

CONCLUSION:

A pilot study of the use of photoactivated disinfection of carious cavities with a solution of tonym chloride showed high efficiency in the prevention of complications in the treatment of deep carious lesions of dentin.

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